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Educational performance and ICTs: availability, use, misuse and context.

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Educational performance and ICTs: availability, use, misuse and context.

Abstract: The relationship between technology and learning is an issue without robust evidence. Previous studies have presented very varied results depending on the learning area, the type of use and the context. This study examines this relationship and the influence of the context, by means of a multilevel analysis of the information in the PISA Report questionnaires for the Spanish regions. The results show that there is a positive relationship for access to technology both at school and at home, and that its educational uses are not more beneficial than its recreational uses. The study also confirms the misuse of technology as a distraction, with saturation thresholds above which their availability and use are detrimental, and that technological devices have different impacts depending on the guidance provided in their use. Finally, the influence of the students' environment on their ICT use is confirmed according to contextual characteristics that affect that guidance.

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1. Introduction

The growing and increasingly early exposure of students to information and communication technologies (ICT) is a source of concern for parents, teachers and all members of the educational community in general.

Indeed, technology may be considered a cultural tool which has the potential to amplify and reorganise cognitive processes; nevertheless, fulfilling this potential depends to an enormous extent on the relationship established with it. As Orhan et al. (2021) show for technology use at work, it has a potential positive productivity and performance effect but also a potential negative overload and distraction effect.

ICTs are not homogeneous, and each instrument is used in a different way. Students with access to ICTs generally seem to perform better in standardised tests (Schater, 1999), but those results depend on the type of device, how they are used and the specific educational context (Higgins, 2012).

As a result, although access to technology at school can potentially improve the teaching-learning process and increase the motivation of students and teachers, there is no clear evidence of how these technological resources should be presented, or their concrete impact on the various subjects (Cox et al., 2003; Condie & Munro, 2007; Claro, 2010).

Using ICTs can help with solving problems and exploring concepts; however, the learning outcome will depend on the relationship established with it and with the context, since they lead to different reactions that affect the involvement and attitudes of those involved (students and teachers) and ultimately educational performance (Barkatsas, Kasimatis & Gialamas, 2009).

The impact of technology on learning is determined by two types of digital divides. The first divide is the result of differences in how students use ICTs due to their membership of social groups with unequal access to them (Bolt & Grawford, 2000).

The second divide is focused on the study of differences in the ability to benefit from ICTs due to disparities in the students' socio-economic and socio-cultural environment. This suggests that diversity in the use of ICTs is motivated not so much by unequal access to them (the "availability effect"), but by differences in the way they are related to, used and exploited (Hargittai, 2003; Hargittai & Hinnant, 2008; Beckman, Bennet & Lockyer, 2014). This could be called a "use effect".

The impact of these "effects" on education is a current and controversial issue. Without clear conclusions of each one separately and with new evidence that both operate together. Since differences in access to ICT generate differences in the student's familiarity with them and, therefore, in their frequency and type of use (Srijamdee & Pholphirul, 2020).

The student's environment appears in both areas of the analysis in this discussion. There are still significant spatial differences in the provision of technology between contexts like home or school and between geographical areas (Wang, Zhou & Wang, 2021). Which could account for the unequal impacts caused by the "availability effect".

However, the context also includes the place where the relationships between the parties involved, and with the tools available, are generated and evolve. These relationships are able to modulate the general adoption and use of technology and the specific application of technology in learning, and to improve or impair its results.

In this vein, studies like Nysveen, Pedersen & Skard (2020) propose that technology adoption is a social and ambient-dependent interaction process of sharing practices in an ecosystem context. While other studies like Cherbib et al. (2021) show, for firm learning with digital

technologies, that the social context and the degree of collaboration in the relationships determine the potential learning benefits of technology.

All of the above means that the context is also a source of inequality in the use of these technologies, based on the "use effect".

1.1. Technology and educational performance: the empirical evidence.

The relationship between ICTs and education is very complex, and depends on various factors. There is extensive empirical evidence in this regard, and its conclusions are also diverse and controversial.

The seminal study by Weglinsky (1998) is considered one of the first to deal with the issue. This research found a positive impact of ICT: in the United States, eighth grade students (13-14 years old) who used technologies at school were almost a third of the year ahead of those who did not use them in their mathematics grades.

Since then, subsequent studies have attempted to improve the definition of how ICTs impact on learning. There are both examples of a positive impact, and others where no evidence for it is reported (Cheung & Slavin, 2013; Mediavilla & Escardíbul, 2014; Petko, Cantieni & Prasse, 2017; Tan & Hew, 2019; Gubbels, Swart & Groen, 2020; Odell, Galovan & Cutumisu, 2020; as reviews of the subject).

The net impact of the availability and use of ICTs in homes and schools on educational results is ambiguous. They do not appear to reduce differences in students' performance in isolation (Bulman & Fairlie, 2016). This depends on the education systems' ability to harness the potential of these technologies (OECD, 2015).

However, recent studies have presented promising conclusions about the role of technology in improving effectiveness and learning outcomes. These studies focus particularly on analysing

which educational interventions assisted with digital devices are successful, and which ones positively affect behaviour, and the students' interaction with them (Escueta, Quan, Nickow & Oreopoulos, 2017; Chauhan, 2017; Lai, 2019; Srijamdee & Pholphirul, 2020).

Many of the studies examined the impact of technology using the PISA test that the OECD performs on 15-year-old students, and found no clear evidence for the influence of technology on educational performance.

For example, the 2003 PISA wave (OECD, 2004) showed a negative result in the performance of students who make little use of technologies at home ("less than once a month") and a very negative result for students who use them very often at school ("almost every day"). Furthermore, the general frequency of use seems to have a non-linear relationship with performance (it is first positive and then negative as the frequency increases), and recreational uses are more beneficial than educational ones.

The 2006 edition (OECD, 2007) found no significant effect of the frequency of access to technology at school, but a negative effect of access at home. The 2009 (OECD, 2010) and 2012 (OECD, 2015) editions showed again a curvilinear relation with a benefit from a moderate ICT exposure versus the lack or excessive exposure.

The 2015 PISA Report (OECD, 2016) presents a widespread positive effect on performance of access to digital devices in the home in comparison to a lack of access to them. However, this depends on the type of device, and is not evident in terms of their use.

In general, the conclusions from the different editions of the PISA Report are ambiguous. The available empirical evidence based on this test finds both positive impacts of technology and negative impacts on its results, and even an absence of impacts (see Table 1 for a summary).

These vary according to whether the competence concerned is science, reading or mathematics (Petko, Cantieni & Prasse, 2017), depending on the digital device (Srijamdee &

Pholphirul, 2020) and whether these technologies are available and used at home or at school (Tan & Hew, 2019) and depending on whether they are used for educational purposes or for entertainment (Gubbels, Swart & Groen, 2020).

-Insert Table 1 here-

In addition, several of these studies find that these relationships are non-linear. They show curvilinear shapes and thresholds that indicate that moderate ICT exposure is generally beneficial but deficits and excesses are detrimental (Gubbels, Swart & Groen, 2020; Srijamdee & Pholphirul, 2020; Vazquez-Cano, Gómez-Galán, Infante-Moro & López-Meneses, 2020).

The context also plays a significant role in these studies. Not only because of the already highlighted differences obtained in contrasting educational contexts such as home and school. But because of the differences found between countries based on their particular socio-economic and socio-cultural contexts: developed and developing countries (Srijamdee & Pholphirul, 2020), confucian and occidental cultures (Tan & Hew, 2019) and different areas of Europe (Bulut & Cutumisu, 2018; Ferraro, 2018; Ozola & Grinfelds, 2018; Odell, Galovan & Cutumisu, 2020).

For the Spanish case the recent evidence from the PISA Report is also mixed, but points to the need of a better ICT integration at school. Mediavilla & Escardíbul (2014) show a positive impact of ICT availability at home and school but a negative one of the frequency of all uses. Alderete, Di Meglio & Formichella (2017) show a positive effect of ICT availability and use out of school and a negative one from the use at school. Rodriguez-Mantilla, Fernández-Díaz & Olmeda (2018) find a positive effect in science scores from ICT availability at home but a

non significant one at school. And Tourón et al. (2018) find that high performance students have more digital devices at home and make a more frequent entertainment use than a educational one.

Given all of the above, the objective of this study is to examine the relationship between ICTs and educational performance, and the factors that affect that relationship using the Spanish PISA database. The study simultaneously measures various aspects that influence the "availability effect" and the "use effect" of technology, and considers the contexts (both inside and outside the classroom) that affect the educational use of technologies in particular depth. Spain is one of those countries belonging to the so-called "European periphery" and Spanish students have less ICT availability at home and their results are equal or below the European average, according to the PISA Report (OECD, 2016). In addition, Spain shows a geographical divide in the provision, application and integration of technologies in education (Garrido & García, 2016; Bravo, Pons & Pagán, 2018). So Spain represent a relevant case of the diversity of countries with any similar characteristics and the obtained results should be generalizable.

In short, this study tests two main hypotheses, which are as follows:

H.1. There is a significant relationship between students' interaction with ICTs and their educational performance, which depends on the knowledge area and the type and frequency of the interaction.

H.1.1. The availability of ICTs is a necessary and beneficial condition. However, their impact on educational performance is more closely related to their use than to mere possession of or access to them. As a result, the "availability effect" on educational performance is positive, but is less intense than the "use effect".

H.1.2. Technology can be used in a beneficial way for learning, but it can also be used as a means of distraction that is detrimental to learning ("misuse"). Educational uses therefore contribute more positively to educational performance than recreational uses. The influence of each technological device also depends on the extent to which its use is open and exposed to these misuses.

H.1.3. An excessive level of availability and frequency of use of technology increases the likelihood of misuse, and may distract the student from other tasks which are as beneficial or more so for their learning. The possible positive links between ICTs and educational performance are therefore weaker or may even be negative after a threshold of saturation in their availability and use has been reached.

H.2. The relationship that students have with ICTs and above all with how they are used is determined by their socio-economic and sociocultural environment. Some environments are more positive for their beneficial use than others.

H.2.1. In environments such as the home, the use of the technology available is subject to less guidance than in other environments such as at school, and misuse is more likely. Access to ICTs in the home is generally less beneficial for educational performance, and misuse occurs earlier and is more detrimental.

H.2.2. Some social, cultural and economic characteristics of environments contexts outside the classroom and the home determine whether they are good guides for the use of technologies. This influences how students use them.

The hypotheses above were tested for three knowledge areas (science, mathematics and reading), assuming that the impact of technology on learning is not the same in each one.

Unlike other studies, all the hypotheses were checked by controlling and isolating

characteristics of students and their families that may influence their relationship with technology, and affect the results.

2. Methodology:

2.1. Sample:

The database used to analyse the relationship between educational performance and technology, and between technology and the environment was the database for the 2015 edition of the PISA Report. This database included an expanded regional sample, in which 35,943 students from 1,089 schools in Spain participated.

The students took a cognitive test for each competence (science, reading, and mathematics), which was a mixture of multiple choice and open questions. These questions had different levels of difficulty and an associated score. The performance of the students in each competence can be evaluated using a plausible value system, on a scale of scores with a mean of 500 and a standard deviation of 100.

The PISA also carries out context questionnaires that provide information about the characteristics of the student, their family and their school, and therefore about the various factors in those areas that could influence their relationship with ICTs and their learning.

The results of the PISA test are available for the 17 Spanish regions, and they can therefore be related to territorial variables, provided by both the Spanish National Statistics Institute and the country's Ministry of Education.

2.2. Variables:

The main dependent variables for classifying educational performance are the student scores in each of the competences examined in the PISA Report mentioned above. In order to

determine the students' interaction with technology, we used part of the context questionnaires related to the availability and use of ICTs at home and at school.

Based on those questionnaires, the PISA Report produces the availability rates for technological devices at home (Icthome) and at school (Ictsch). These are obtained by adding together the number of devices mentioned by the students as available in the constituent items (Table II). Values between 0 (no device available) and 11 or 10 (all devices available) are assigned respectively.

In the questionnaires, students are also asked about how often they use technological devices outside school for activities considered as leisure (ranging from playing video games to downloading applications onto their mobile telephone) and for schoolwork (ranging from browsing the Internet to do their homework to downloading science applications onto their mobile telephone). They are also asked about how frequently they use technological devices at school in general.

The OECD applies a scaling methodology according to the Item Response Theory to the relevant items above (Table 2) to construct the frequency rates for ICT use outside school for entertainment (Entuse), outside school for schoolwork (Homesch) and at school in general (Usesch); respectively. The scale reliability (Cronbach's Alpha coefficient) of the ICT resources is 0.555 in Spain, similar or even higher than in other analysed European countries.

All of the above assume variables which are derived from the subjective questionnaires completed by the students. This information may therefore be biased in terms of the real situation based on the students' perceptions; especially as regards the use of ICTs. This is one of the main limitations of this research.

Variables were used to characterise the environment apart from the classroom and the home which attempt to show the extent to which the environment is favourable for the use of ICTs.

A favourable environment is deemed to be one in where the student lives, and where ICT sectors and users have a leading role among the population the student relates to.

Based on this approach, the estimate included variables for the territorial context, such as the population's level of education (the proportion of the population having completed higher education, and students in STEM degree courses); the labour market situation (the proportion of those employed in the ICT and R+D sectors); the type of business activity (the proportion of innovative companies and those in high-tech sectors); the innovative climate (total expenditure on R+D and innovative intensity of companies) and the availability and use of technological devices and services in businesses and in homes.

Finally, unlike other studies, control variables that include the student's characteristics and those of their family which can influence the individual's educational performance and their relationship with ICT were included. According to the literature (Gubbels, Swart & Groen, 2020), controls were performed for gender (Barkatsas, Kasimatis & Gialamas, 2009), socio-economic and cultural level (Beckman et al., 2014) and ethnicity (Park, Lawson & Williams, 2012).

-Insert Table 2 here-

2.3.Procedure:

Given the hierarchical structure of the data (students within schools within regions), compliance with the principle of independence of observations is difficult. Students from the same school, and schools from the same region, will therefore tend to present characteristics and results that are more similar than those from different schools and regions.

It is advisable to use multilevel techniques that take this nesting of the units of analysis at higher levels into account to avoid estimation biases (Hox, 1995). We decided to apply a hierarchical or multilevel linear model with the form (Equation 1):

$$Y_{ijk} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{1ijk} + \beta_2 X_{2ijk} + \beta_3 X_{3ijk} + \beta_4 X_{4ijk} + \mu_j + \mu_k + \varepsilon_{ijk} \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

Where i refers to the student, j to the school and k to the region (the three levels of nesting) and Y_{ijk} is the dependent variable. The fixed part of the model consists of X_{1ijk} and X_{2ijk} , the variables associated with the student and their family; X_{3ijk} , the variables related to the school environment; and X_{4ijk} , the variables associated with the regional context, while the random part consists of μ_j and μ_k , the random constants of the school level (second level) and the region (third level); and ε_{ijk} , the error term.

In order to test the hypotheses presented, the estimation strategy involves making three different estimates:

1. The first estimate examines the general relationship between educational performance and ICTs, using the score for the various competences as dependent variables, which are explained based on the availability and frequency of use of ICTs.
2. The second estimate studies the specific relationship between educational performance and various technological devices, and also uses the score for the various competences as dependent variables. However, they are explained according to the availability and use of each device.
3. The final estimate examines the relationship between ICT use and the environment, and uses the frequency indices of the various uses of ICTs as dependent variables, which are explained based on the different variables of the environment.

The applied procedure together with the cross-section database implies that the analysis and results are correlational, and that causality cannot be established. This is the second main limitation of this research.

3. Results:

The results of the first estimate (Figure 1 and Table A.1) confirm the significance of the relationship between educational performance and technology, after taking the control variables into consideration, which is particularly evident when performance in science competence is analysed. However, contrary to expectations based on the empirical evidence available, it is also more significant for reading literacy and for mathematics to a lesser extent.

Greater availability of technological resources both at home and at school is generally associated with higher levels of educational performance among students, indicating the existence of a positive "availability effect".

However, this association is not linear: the mere accumulation of technological devices makes an increasingly smaller contribution to improving performance, until saturation is reached, at which point they no longer make a contribution, and may even be detrimental.

Technology has a different impact at school and at home. The contribution made by each additional device is significantly greater at school, although improvements come to an end earlier than at home (Figure 1a).

The use of ICTs has a relationship with educational performance which is similar to the availability effect, albeit somewhat more intense, consistent with the range of its contribution to the score and the coefficients estimated in the model. The relationship is once again non-linear.

Moderate and guided use of ICTs (at school or when they have to be used for schoolwork at home) has one of the best impacts. At around an average frequency of use (zero on the X axis in Figure 1b), the impact is slightly positive at school and somewhat greater at home.

However, more than moderate but less than abusive leisure use has even a better positive impact.

Perhaps the most interesting finding in our results is related to the abuse of technology, as when the levels of educational uses are clearly above average, the impact on performance becomes strongly negative, especially at home. This may indicate the importance of guidance and contexts for making good use of ICTs to improve students' learning.

-Insert Figure 1 here-

In contrast to the above, the results of the second estimate (Figure 2 and table A.2) contain important differences in the relationship with educational performance, depending on the type of technological device and the context in which the student interacts with them. Which are more relevant in overall terms for science and reading than for mathematics.

Devices which are generally used in a more guided way are clearly less likely to be misused and present greater benefits for learning. This effect is amplified in more formal learning environment such as at school, where teachers guide activities involving technology and restrict misuse, and where the availability of these devices is more closely related to their use by students.

Students with access to computers connected to the Internet at school perform better, regardless of whether they report using them. The availability of a projector at school is strongly associated with higher levels of performance, and these are even higher if students

report using it. The availability of digital whiteboards at school is positively associated with all the literacies, although this association negative when their use is reported (possibly because they are often used as a much more complex substitute for the projector).

However, the mere availability of other devices and "free" use of them does not predict a positive link to performance. The availability of technologies such as Wi-Fi at school, which are subject to less control and are more conducive to abuse is independent of educational performance, and their use has a considerably detrimental effect.

The importance of learning environments when assessing the importance of ICTs is apparent when considering the home. There is a greater propensity for misuse in the home, where the guidelines for making educational use of technology are weaker. Access to technological devices in this context does not guarantee any result, and neither does the use of them. The combination of "free" use technologies, such as desktop computers and the Internet in these less guided environments can be particularly detrimental for educational performance.

-Insert Figure 2 here-

The distinction between guided contexts and freer contexts can be transferred into any of the student's environments apart from the school and home. As a result, some characteristics of these environments make them better or worse guides, and affect the educational use of ICTs. This is confirmed by the results of the third estimate (Table A.3), which shows the existence of various socio-economic and socio-cultural aspects in the territorial context which have a significant relationship with the frequency with which students use technology, and especially with educational uses.

A higher level of education among the population is associated with a lower frequency of all the uses that students make of technologies, and a large number of innovative companies is linked to an increased use of ICTs in general, and especially of educational uses. The opposite applies to technology companies.

Despite the fact that research budget intensity is positively correlated with the frequency of ICT use in general, it has a negative correlation with innovative intensity in companies. The availability and use of ICTs in homes and businesses are also relevant factors, and the availability and quality of the Internet connection and the use of ICTs for everyday tasks (such as online shopping or electronic invoices) are particularly important.

4. Discussion and Conclusions:

This study contributes to expand the existing knowledge on the relationship between ICTs and educational performance in various knowledge areas, and in particular, to identify the influence of the context on students' use of technologies. For that purpose, the Spanish PISA case is used as a relevant representative of any other country that belongs to the European periphery, is below average in ICT home availability, is similar or below average in PISA scores or has a significant geographical digital divide.

The relationship obtained in this study between educational performance and the availability and use of technological devices is shown to be highly significant and subject to multiple factors, confirming the first main hypothesis (H.1.). However, this relationship does not entirely agree with the relationship mentioned in its secondary hypotheses.

Having more technological devices both at home and at school in particular is associated with better educational results. There is a positive availability effect of a considerable magnitude, but it is less intense than the use effect (H.1.1.). This results contrast with the ones obtained

by Odell, Galovan & Cutumisu (2020) for Bulgaria and Finland, and seems to justify public policies aimed at making technology available at homes and, specially, at schools.

The type of use made of technology is crucial in its influence on learning. There is evidence of both educationally beneficial uses and detrimental uses and abuse (H.1.2.). However, the supposedly more educational uses of technology (for schoolwork at home and at school in general) do not appear to be clearly more beneficial than recreational use.

These results contrast with other international evidence (Vazquez-Cano, Gómez-Galán, Infante-Moro & López-Meneses, 2020) but are consistent with the Spanish evidence (Tourón et al., 2018) and with propositions about game-based learning and gamification (Huizenga, Ten Dam, Voogt, & Admiraal, 2017). They highlight the need for a reformulation and instruction on the use of ICTs from the strictly educational sphere, aimed at incorporating content that appeals to students, but which retains a pedagogical function.

Furthermore, similar to that obtained in Thailand by Srijamdee & Pholpirul (2020), each technological device has a different influence. Which here is proposed as determined by how guided its use is and the context in which it is used. There is a distinction between guided uses and contexts, which are focused on learning with some control over distractions, and freer uses, where the student is self-directed and is at greater risk of distraction. This distinction is another contribution of this paper, as it goes beyond the scope of the analysis on the impact of the availability and use of ICTs in the literature.

The results above highlight the importance of education in the use of technology, in order to take full advantage of the immense potential for learning it provides and to avoid the disadvantages arising from its misuse. Public policies must consider the advisability of the endowment and promotion of the use of those harmful devices, and proceed with caution as regards those with doubtful effects and facilitate the use of those that are clearly beneficial.

It would be particularly useful to carry out awareness-raising campaigns about the potential and risks of students' exposure to ICTs, accompanied by the appropriate recommendations enabling and encouraging informed parental action, and to establish an appropriate training plan for teachers on the use of technology in schools. This should instruct them not only on the use of each specific device, but on the potential for its educational application.

As Gubbels, Swart & Groen (2020) find for Netherlands, there are non-linear effects in the relationship between the availability and use of ICTs and educational performance.

Accumulating devices makes an increasingly smaller contribution to results until a saturation point is reached, when they no longer make a contribution and even become detrimental (H.1.3.).

Caution should therefore always be exercised when encouraging students to use ICTs and especially with regards how these public policies aimed at the availability of technology are implemented in the long term, given the possible detrimental effects of an accumulation of these devices in environments where there is already a sufficient amount of them.

The second main hypothesis (H.2.) is also confirmed. Some differences were found in the use of technology in education depending on the student's context, and according to how intense and positive the environment is for guiding this use.

According to the first of the secondary hypotheses (H.2.1.), the misuse of ICTs is less common and less intense in more guided contexts, and its relationship with educational performance is more positive. In contrast with previous Spanish evidence (Rodríguez-Mantilla, Fernández-Díaz & Olmeda, 2018), ICTs are more effective and used to better advantage in school, where they are more guided towards learning and their misuse can be prevented due to being in a more supervised environment.

School plays an important role, not only because these tools are used for learning various subjects there, but also because it teaches students how to use them properly in other areas. As a guided environment par excellence, school can contribute to improving performance in the use of ICTs in other environments, where technology is present to a lesser extent.

Our results show a significant relationship between different social, cultural and economic aspects of the context and the students' frequency of use of technologies (H.2.2.). This agrees with previous approaches about differences in ICT use by country characteristics (Bulut & Cutumisu, 2018; Tan & Hew, 2019; Odell, Galovan & Cutumisu, 2020), but here a deeper level of spatial disaggregation is applied and many more context characteristics are included.

In specific terms, the particular characteristics in the population's level of education, the type of business activity, the innovative climate and the availability and use of ICTs in homes and businesses are factors closely related to it, primarily in educational uses.

All the environments that surround students when they use technology are therefore important once again. This is particularly true for the characteristics of the environments which make them better or worse guides for their use in learning.

Finally, the possible subjective nature of the source of the surveys and the cross section of the information used have been highlighted as the two major limitations of this study. However, since they are also widely used in the specific literature, we believe that they do not invalidate the results obtained.

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Tables

Table 1. Synthesis of some international studies on the effect of technology on the PISA test

Effect Type	Study	ICT Variables	Competence
Positive	Spiezia (2010)	Availability and use of computer by educational context	Science
	Ferraro (2018)	Availability at school	Mathematics
Negative or null	Wittwer & Senkbeil (2008)	Availability and frequency of use at home	Mathematics
	Aypay (2010)	Type of use	Mathematics
	Biagi & Loi (2012)	Type of use	Mathematics, Science and Reading
	Ozola & Grinfelds (2018)	Use at school	Reading
	Odell, Galovan & Cutumisu (2020)	General availability and use	Science
Conditional	Fuchs & Woessman (2004)	Availability, type of use by educational context	Mathematics and Reading
	Papanastasiou et al. (2005)	Type of use	Mathematics and Science
	Papanastasiou & Ferdig (2006)	Concrete tasks	Mathematics and Science
	Petko, Cantieni & Prasse (2017)	Type of use by educational and country context	Mathematics, Science and Reading
	Bulut & Cutumisu (2018)	Availability, type of use by educational and country context	Mathematics and Science
	Tan & Hew (2019)	Availability and type of use by educational and country context	
	Gubbels, Swart & Groen (2020)	Availability and type of use by educational context	Reading
	Srijamdee & Pholpirul (2020)	Concrete digital devices and concrete tasks by educational context	Mathematics, Science and Reading
	Vazquez-Cano, Gómez-Galán, Infante-Moro & López-Meneses (2020)	Availability and leisure use	Reading

Source: own elaboration.

Table 2. Composition and code of ICT Indices on PISA

Indicator	Index	Item	Item Coding
Availability	Icthome	<i>ic001q01ta- ic001q11ta</i>	1: availability and use of the device. 2: availability without use. 3: unavailability.
	Ictsch	<i>ic009q01ta- ic009q11na</i>	
Use	Entuse	<i>ic008q01ta- ic008q13na</i>	From 1 (“Never or almost never”) to 5 (“Everyday”) according to the frequency of the task
	Homesch	<i>ic010q01ta- ic010q12na</i>	
	Usesch	<i>ic011q01ta- ic011q09ta</i>	

Source: own elaboration from PISA 2015 Codebook.

Figures

Figure 1. Estimated contribution of ICT Indices to performance in scientific competence

Source: own elaboration from PISA 2015 data.

Figure 2. Estimated contribution of each device to performance in scientific competence

Source: own elaboration from PISA 2015 data.

Appendix

Table A.1. Multilevel estimation for the relationship between technology and educational performance

Fixed Effects Parameters		Science		Reading		Mathematics	
Variables		Coeff	Signif	Coeff	Signif	Coeff	Signif
Control	<i>Woman</i>	-14.26	***	11.12	***	-17.81	***
	<i>ESCS</i>	20.03	***	19.19	***	19.19	***
	<i>Immigrant 2nd Gen</i>	-16.94	***	-9.98	***	-15.53	***
	<i>Immigrant 1st Gen</i>	-29.06	***	-23.00	***	-33.23	***
ICT Availability	<i>At Home</i>	10.96	***	11.92	***	9.32	***
	<i>At Home^2</i>	-0.60	***	-0.69	***	-0.44	***
	<i>At School</i>	19.32	***	20.88	***	15.56	***
	<i>At School^2</i>	-2.05	***	-2.13	***	-1.68	***
ICT Use	<i>Schoolwork at Home</i>	-6.39	***	-6.95	***	-4.68	***
	<i>Schoolwork at Home^2</i>	-3.58	***	-3.93	***	-3.56	***
	<i>Entertainment at Home</i>	6.28	***	6.20	***	3.03	***
	<i>Entertainment at Home^2</i>	-1.65	***	-1.65	***	-1.37	***
	<i>At School in General</i>	-2.37	***	-3.07	***	-0.43	-
	<i>At School in General^2</i>	-2.38	***	-3.22	***	-2.28	***
<i>Constant Term</i>		450.29	***	431.66	***	452.73	***
Random Effects Parameter (Variances)		Science		Reading		Mathematics	
Level		Null	Final	Null	Final	Null	Final
<i>Region (Constant Term)</i>		167.04	78.06	142.70	53.33	212.55	122.35
<i>School (Constant Term)</i>		721.46	178.90	761.25	179.24	628.08	134.64
<i>Individual (Residual)</i>		6033.36	4746.72	5578.49	4200.80	4975.76	3860.46
Model Adjustment		Science		Reading		Mathematics	
<i>Log Likelihood</i>		-146843.18		-145287.76		-144152.21	
<i>Wald Test: Chi2 (14)</i>		5851.5	***	6555.8	***	6635.9	***
<i>LR vs Lineal Test: Chi2 (2)</i>		654.4	***	567.7	***	876.3	***

Source: own elaboration from PISA 2015 data. Significance level: ***1% **5% *10%.

Table A.2. Multilevel estimation for the relationship between some technology devices and educational performance

Fixed Effects Parameters		Science		Reading		Mathematics	
Variables		Coeff	Signif	Coeff	Variables	Coeff	Signif
Control	<i>Woman</i>	-12.61	***	13.06	***	-16.09	***
	<i>ESCS</i>	20.50	***	19.63	***	19.53	***
	<i>Immigrant 2nd Gen</i>	-14.71	***	-7.92	***	-13.26	***
	<i>Immigrant 1st Gen</i>	-26.98	***	-20.94	***	-31.17	***
Availability at Home	<i>Desktop Computer</i>	-3.62	***	-5.56	***	1.07	-
	<i>Laptop</i>	2.26	-	2.99	**	0.01	-
	<i>Internet</i>	-42.24	***	-49.81	***	-28.03	***
	<i>Tablet</i>	1.72	-	-1.98	*	1.48	-
	<i>Ebook</i>	0.11	-	0.27	-	4.19	***
Availability at School	<i>Computer with Internet</i>	14.19	***	14.52	***	13.77	***
	<i>Wifi</i>	-1.47	-	2.15	*	0.04	-
	<i>Projector</i>	17.36	***	19.14	***	14.77	***
	<i>Digital Whiteboard</i>	4.51	***	4.61	***	5.11	***
Availability and Use at Home	<i>Desktop Computer</i>	-7.94	***	-10.57	***	-3.61	***
	<i>Laptop</i>	-2.71	**	-0.20	-	-0.68	-
	<i>Internet</i>	15.81	***	15.34	***	15.32	***
	<i>Tablet</i>	-13.74	***	-13.97	***	-12.12	***
	<i>Ebook</i>	1.19	-	-0.95	-	1.71	*
Availability and Use at School	<i>Computer with Internet</i>	12.43	***	12.14	***	11.58	***
	<i>Wifi</i>	-18.16	***	-14.92	***	-15.54	***
	<i>Projector</i>	48.06	***	47.67	***	41.78	***
	<i>Digital Whiteboard</i>	-10.04	***	-9.93	***	-8.13	***
<i>Constant Term</i>		486.42	***	473.98	***	477.57	***
Random Effects Parameter (Variances)		Science		Reading		Mathematics	
Level		Null	Final	Null	Final	Null	Final
<i>Region (Constant Term)</i>		167.04	87.27	142.70	62.86	212.55	130.88
<i>School (Constant Term)</i>		721.46	199.03	761.25	213.09	628.08	149.69
<i>Individual (Residual)</i>		6033.36	4835.92	5578.49	4391.73	4975.76	3900.31
Model Adjustment		Science		Reading		Mathematics	
<i>Log Likelihood</i>		-164214.24		-162862.47		-161090.55	
<i>Wald Test: Chi2 (22)</i>		6554.2	***	6768.6	***	7568.3	***
<i>LR vs Lineal Test: Chi2 (2)</i>		4835.9	***	792.0	***	1093.8	***

Source: own elaboration from PISA 2015 data. Significance level: ***1% **5% *10%.

Table A.3. Multilevel estimation for the relationship between territorial context and use of ICT

Fixed Effects Parameters		Schoolwork at Home		Entertainment at Home		At School in General	
Variables		Coeff	Signif	Coeff	Variables	Coeff	Signif
Control	<i>Woman</i>	-0.02	**	-0.25	***	-0.04	***
	<i>ESCS</i>	0.04	***	0.02	***	0.01	*
	<i>Immigrant 2nd Gen</i>	0.17	***	0.11	***	0.08	**
	<i>Immigrant 1st Gen</i>	0.15	***	0.12	***	0.02	-
ICT Availability	<i>At Home</i>	0.07	***	0.08	***	0.02	***
	<i>At School</i>	0.07	***	0.02	***	0.10	***
Regional Context	<i>Higher Education</i>	-0.07	***	-0.02	-	-0.05	*
	<i>STEM Studies</i>	0.02	***	-0.01	-	0.01	-
	<i>ICT Employment</i>	0.00	-	-0.03	-	-0.12	***
	<i>R&D Employment</i>	-0.18	-	-0.13	-	0.01	-
	<i>Innovative Companies</i>	0.45	***	0.20	***	0.55	***
	<i>High Tech Companies</i>	-0.50	*	-0.74	***	-1.53	***
	<i>R&D Expenditure</i>	<0.01	*	<0.01	**	<0.01	**
	<i>Innovative Intensity</i>	-0.27	**	-0.20	**	-0.40	***
	<i>Companies with Internet & Web</i>	0.01	-	0.02	***	0.02	***
	<i>Companies with Social Networks</i>	0.02	***	-0.01	***	0.01	-
	<i>Electronic Bill</i>	-0.01	***	0.00	-	-0.02	***
	<i>Homes with High Speed Broadband</i>	0.01	*	0.01	*	0.01	*
	<i>Social Networks at Home</i>	-0.01	**	0.00	-	0.00	-
	<i>Electronic Banking</i>	-0.01	***	0.00	-	0.00	-
<i>Online Shopping</i>	0.01	***	-0.01	*	0.01	**	
<i>Constant Term</i>		-0.92	**	-0.37	-	-1.61	***
Random Effects Parameter (Variances)		Schoolwork at Home		Entertainment at Home		School in General	
Level		Null	Final	Null	Final	Null	Final
<i>Region (Constant Term)</i>		0.01	<0.01	0.01	<0.01	0.02	<0.01
<i>School (Constant Term)</i>		0.05	0.04	0.01	0.01	0.09	0.08
<i>Individual (Residual)</i>		0.70	0.64	0.68	0.62	0.64	0.58
Model Adjustment		Schoolwork at Home		Entertainment at Home		School in General	
<i>Log Likelihood</i>		-31594.58		-31391.84		-30796.51	
<i>Wald Test: Chi2 (21)</i>		1815.1	***	1791.4	***	2017.2	***
<i>LR vs Lineal Test: Chi2 (2)</i>		518.9	***	56.5	***	1722.9	***

Source: own elaboration from PISA 2015 data. Significance level: ***1% **5% *10%.